

Code System for Interactional Features

Code System	Memo
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move	<p>Definition: Recasts are episodes in which the interlocutor rephrases the learner's preceding utterance that contains at least one error to be more target-like by changing one or more sentence components while retaining its central meaning and without breaking the flow of the communication.</p> <p>A recast consists of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the trigger utterance (i.e., the learner utterance containing one or more errors), • the interlocutor's recast move (i.e., the interlocutor utterance containing the recast form, i.e., the recast form), • the learner's response to the feedback (i.e., uptake of the recast form) or the learner's or interlocutor's topic continuation move <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the interlocutor's recast move (i.e., the interlocutor utterance containing the recast form). • The entire interlocutor's turn is coded including timestamps. • The code is only assigned if the recast move occurs within one turn of the trigger utterance. <p>Note: Utterances as complete semantic units are contained in the chat messages (i.e., the sent text visible on the screen often marked with a time stamp, corresponding to one line in the MAXQDA script).</p> <p>Each chat message may contain a single utterance (e.g., 'How may I help you?') or more than one utterance (e.g., 'Hello, i want to reservate a room an need your help.'). An utterance may also be split across two or more messages.</p> <p>The messages make up the learners' and interlocutors' turns. A turn is defined here as a transfer of the 'floor' from one interlocutor to the other. A turn may consist of a single chat message or a sequence of messages by the same interlocutor ("split turn"). A message sequence that is</p>

interrupted by a message sent by the interlocutor resulting in an overlap is not considered as separate turns but as part of the same split turn.

Examples:

User: Yes how much is the costen [lexis error] for this room?

Bot: The price [recast form] is CHF 1100 CHF for room Gamma. [recast move]

User: Have you got any rooms with space for at least 150 Peoples [grammatical error]?

Bot: Yes, certainly.

Bot: We have three rooms that are suitable for None quests.

Bot: Room Alpha has space for up to 270 people [recast form].

Bot: The Beta room has space for a total of 190 people [recast form], indoor and outdoor.

Bot: There is space for 200 people [recast form] in room Gamma. [recast move]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Linguistic focus

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Recasts\Recast
move\Linguistic focus\Grammar

Definition: The recast addresses one or more grammatical errors in the learner's utterance.

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the entire recast move including time stamp.
- When the learner's turn contains errors of different types (e.g., grammar, spelling, and lexis) but the interlocutor recasts only one of the error types (e.g., grammar), code according to the error type addressed in the recast (e.g., "Grammar").
- When the interlocutor recasts more than one error type (e.g., spelling and lexis), assign code "Multi-focus".

Example:

User: How about the [grammatical error] room Beta

Bot: Room Beta [recast form] has a portable screen, a projector, and loudspeakers. [recast move with grammar focus]

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Recasts\Recast
move\Linguistic focus\Spelling

Definition: The recast addresses one or more spelling errors in the learner's utterance.

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the entire recast move including time stamp.
- When the learner's turn contains errors of different types (e.g., grammar, spelling, and lexis) but the interlocutor recasts only one of the error types (e.g., grammar), code according to the error type addressed by the recast (e.g., "Grammar").
- When the interlocutor recasts more than one error type (e.g., spelling and lexis), assign code "Multi-focus".

Example:

User: Yes, but in the Beta rooms ist [spelling error] just for 130 persons

Bot: Room Beta has a terrace that can hold up to 60 people. The room itself is [recast form] for 130 people. So in total room Beta provides space for 190 guests. [recast move with spelling focus]

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Recasts\Recast
move\Linguistic focus\Lexis

Definition: The recast addresses one or more lexical errors in the learner's utterance.

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the entire recast move including time stamp.
- When the learner's turn contains errors of different types (e.g., grammar, spelling, and lexis) but the interlocutor recasts only one of the error types (e.g., grammar), code according to the error type addressed by the recast (e.g., "Grammar").
- When the interlocutor recasts more than one error type (e.g., spelling and lexis), assign code "Multi-focus".

Example:

User: thats right can you reservate [lexis error] the room please

Bot: For what date would you like to reserve [recast form] room Gamma?

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Linguistic focus\Multi-focus</p>	<p>Definition: The recast addresses more than one error type in the learner's utterance.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the code to the entire recast move including time stamp. • When the learner's turn contains errors of different types (e.g., grammar, spelling, and lexis) but the interlocutor recasts only one of the error types (e.g., grammar), code according to the error type addressed by the recast (e.g., "Grammar"). • When the interlocutor recasts more than one error type (e.g., spelling and lexis), assign code "Multi-focus". <p>Example:</p> <p>User: Yes, but <u>in</u> [grammar error 1] the Beta rooms [grammar error 2] <u>ist</u> [spelling error] just for 130 <u>persons</u> [grammar error 3]</p> <p>Bot: Room Beta has a terrace that can hold up to 60 people [recast form grammar error 3]. <u>The</u> [recast form grammar error 1] <u>room</u> [recast form grammar error 2] <u>itself is</u> [recast form spelling error] for 130 people [recast form grammar error 3].</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Intensity</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\ \Intensity of recast</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Intensity\Intensity of recast\Singular incidence</p>	<p>Definition: None of the erroneous linguistic forms that are addressed in the recast sequence are addressed again in any other recast sequence within the interaction.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire recast sequence including time stamp. Also assign the code when the erroneous form is addressed along with other errors within one sequence.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Intensity\Intensity of recast\Repeated incidence</p>	<p>Definition: At least one erroneous linguistic form that is addressed in the recast sequence is also addressed in another recast sequence within the interaction.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Also assign the code when the erroneous form is addressed along with other 'new' errors. Assign the code to the entire recast sequence including time stamp.</p> <p>Example:</p>

	<p>Message 33: User: and how is <u>the</u> [error] room alpha? <u>Message 34: Bot: Room Alpha [recast form] would be CHF 1400. [Recast sequence 1]</u> Messages 35-40: [...] Message 41: User: can you give me some informations about <u>the</u> [grammar error] room Beta <u>Message 42: Bot: Room Beta [recast form] is on the 15th floor and oversees the entire city. It has a modern ambience and connects to a lovely outside terrace. [Recast sequence 2]</u></p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Intensity\Intensity of recast form</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Intensity\Intensity of recast form\Singular incidence</p>	<p>Definition: None of the recast forms occur more than once in the same recast move.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including the time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: and what about <u>the</u> [error] Alpha? <u>Bot: Room Alpha [recast form] is a spacious room located on the basement floor of the hotel. It is an auditorium furnished with a stage, rows of seats, and a multimedia and lighting system.</u></p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Intensity\Intensity of recast form\Repeated incidence</p>	<p>Definition: At least one of the recast forms is repeated at least once in the same recast move.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including the time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: Which room <u>have</u> [error] the best atmosphere? <u>Bot: Room Alpha is a spacious auditorium on the basement floor with comfortable seating and a stage. It is equipped with multimedia facilities and a lighting system.</u> <u>Bot: Beta has [recast form 1] a modern touch. It is located on the 15th floor and offers incredible views. The glass roof brings in natural light and creates a beautiful atmosphere.</u> <u>Bot: Room Gamma has [recast form 2] the original decoration from the 1920s which gives the room an elegant look.</u></p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Completeness</p>	

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Completeness\Complete	<p>Definition: Recast sequences where all errors of the learner's utterance are addressed.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Completeness\Partial	<p>Definition: Recast sequences where one or more errors of the learner's utterance are left unaddressed.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Length	<p>Definition: The recast move consists of a single sentence consisting of one or more clauses marked by sentence-boundary punctuation, i.e., period, question mark, or exclamation mark.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Length\Single sentence	<p>User: Does the room Alpha <u>has</u> [error] enough space for 150 people? Bot: Room Alpha provides space for up to 270 people. [recast move]</p>

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Length\Multiple sentences	<p>Definition: The recast move consists of more than one sentence in a single message.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Recast move\Length\Multiple messages	<p>Definition: The recast move consists of multiple messages.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Code the entire recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: and what about <u>the</u> [error] Alpha?</p> <p><u>Bot: Room Alpha is a spacious room located on the basement floor of the hotel. It is an auditorium furnished with a stage, rows of seats, and a multimedia and lighting system.</u> [recast move]</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\No uptake	<p>Definition: The recast is not acknowledged and the recast form does not occur anywhere in the learner's production after the recast move, neither in the learner turn immediately following the recast move nor in the further course of the interaction.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire learner turn following the recast move including time stamps. When the recast move occurs at the end of the interaction without learner's response, assign the code to the recast move instead.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: yes, i will book <u>the</u> [error] alpha on the 12 October 2019</p> <p>Bot: Would you like me to book room Alpha [recast] for the 12 October 2019?</p>

	<p><u>User: yes</u> [no uptake] Bot: Thank you, the room has been booked for you. Bot: Could I help you with anything else? User: no, thank you very much and have a nice day. see you soon Bot: We are looking forward to welcoming you at One King Hotel. Goodbye. [final message of interaction – no delayed uptake]</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Immediate uptake	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Immediate uptake\Repair	<p>Definition: The response move (i.e., the learner's turn immediately following the recast move) contains the recast form or forms.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire learner turn following the recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: is alpha allready booked <u>at</u> [error] the 12. October 2019? Bot: So, I will book room Alpha <u>on</u> [recast form] the 12 October 2019 for you. Could you please confirm if you would like me to proceed? <u>User: yes, i will book the alpha on the 12 October 2019</u> [immediate uptake with repair]</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Immediate uptake\Needs repair	<p>Definition: The response move (i.e., the learner's turn immediately following the recast move) contains the recast form or forms with the original error or a new error.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire learner turn following the recast move including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: How about <u>the</u> [error] room Gamma Bot: <u>Room Gamma</u> [recast form] is a spacious room with tables for up to eight people. All the furniture can be moved.</p>

	<p><u>User: That sounds great. Is the room gamma fancy or like a normal room</u> [immediate uptake needs repair]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Delayed uptake</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Delayed uptake\Repair</p>	<p>Definition: The learner produces the recast form or forms later in the interaction rather than in the learner's turn immediately following the recast move.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire learner turn that contains the recast form including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: How about <u>the</u> [error] room Gamma? Bot: <u>Room Gamma</u> [recast form] has room for 200 guests. User: Is it good for presentations? [no immediate uptake] Bot: Room Gamma has space for 200 people. User: is it good for presentations? Bot: Room Gamma has room for 200 guests. User: Is Video and Audio player available? Bot: Could you tell me which room you are interested in? <u>User: Room gamma</u> [delayed uptake with repair]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Delayed uptake\Needs repair</p>	<p>Definition: The learner produces the recast form or forms with the original error or a new error in a turn later in the interaction, i.e., after the turn immediately following the recast move.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire learner turn that contains the erroneous recast form including time stamps.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: How about <u>the</u> [error] Room alpha? Bot: Room Alpha [recast form] is a spacious room located on the basement floor of the hotel. It is an auditorium furnished with a stage, rows of seats, and a multimedia and lighting system. User: Is it possible to have smalltalk with little groups of people? [no immediate uptake]</p>

Bot: Alpha has fixed seating and no tables. It is an auditorium with a stage and rows of seats.
 User: How about the room Gamma [delayed uptake needs repair]

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Re-
 uptake'

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Re-
 e-uptake\Repair

Definition: The next time the recast form or forms occurs in the learner production after immediate or delayed uptake, it is/they are target-like.

Coding guideline:

- The code is assigned to the entire learner turn including time stamp.
- When the recast form occurs more than once in the learner production following immediate or delayed uptake, only the first occurrence is considered.

Example:

User: How about the [error] room Gamma?
 Bot: Room Gamma [recast form] has room for 200 guests.
 User: Is it good for presentations? [no immediate uptake]
 Bot: Room Gamma has space for 200 people.
 User: is it good for presentations? [no uptake]
 Bot: Room Gamma has room for 200 guests.
 User: Is Video and Audio player available? [no uptake]
 Bot: Could you tell me which room you are interested in?
 User: Room gamma [delayed uptake with repair]
 Bot: Room Gamma has two large portable screens and loudspeakers.
 User: How much does room gamma ['re-uptake' with repair] cost?

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Recasts\Uptake\Uptake\Re-
 e-uptake\Needs repair

Definition: The next time the learner produces the recast form or forms after immediate or delayed uptake, it contains/they contain the original error or a new error.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire learner turn including time stamp. When the recast form occurs more than once in the learner production following immediate or delayed uptake, only the first occurrence is considered.

Example:

	<p>User: How about <u>the</u> [error] room Beta Bot: Room Beta [recast form] has a portable screen, a projector, and loudspeakers. User: Does room beta [immediate uptake with repair] have enough space to fit 150 people in it? Bot: Room Beta has space for 130 guests and a terrace for an additional 60 people. <u>User: How about the</u> ['re-uptake' needs repair] <u>room Gamma?</u></p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning	<p>Definition: Episodes where an explicit indication of non-understanding occurs and the conversation is 'pushed down' while the interlocutors attempt to resolve the communication breakdown.</p> <p>A negotiation of meaning episode consists of four components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • trigger (i.e., utterance or part of the utterance that creates non-understanding) • indicator (i.e., utterance that signals that something in a previous utterance was not understood) • response (i.e., utterance that replies to the indicator of non-understanding) • reaction to response (i.e., utterance that contains a reaction to the response) <p>Multi-layered negotiations involve multiple embedded negotiation sequences, whereas single-layered negotiations consist of a single sequence.</p> <p>Coding guidelines: Negotiation episodes are identified by first locating the indicator. From there, the trigger in an earlier utterance is coded, before coding the response and optional reaction to response.</p> <p>In multi-layered negotiation sequences where the same turn corresponds to a certain component (e.g., response) in the first negotiation sequence and another component (e.g., indicator) in the second negotiation sequence, assign each respective code to the turn.</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Trigger	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Trigger\Erroneous	<p>Definition: The trigger, i.e., utterance in a negotiation of meaning episode that creates non-understanding, contains at least one grammatical, lexical, or spelling error and/or discourse error (i.e., unclear meaning or reference, missing contextual relevance).</p> <p>Coding guideline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code the entire turn including timestamp.

- Also consider discourse errors which were not pre-coded.

Examples:

User: How many People can stay here? [erroneous trigger]

Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase?

User: Alright. It is possible to remove the decorations and put something new of the year 2000?
[erroneous trigger]

Bot: Could you please give me the date for the reservation?

Bot: Yes, absolutely.

Bot: There are two rooms available for None people.

Bot: There is space for 270 people in room Alpha.

Bot: Room Gamma offers space for up to 200 people.

User: I need to make a presentation [erroneous trigger (insufficient context)]

Bot: Could you tell me which room you are interested in?

User: The reservation is for 12 october 2019

Bot: Please could you confirm if you would like to book room Alpha for the 12 october 2019?

Bot: Room Alpha has a big screen and a state-of-the-art projector and audio system.

Bot: It is possible to add a portable screen as well as projector and loudspeakers to Beta. [erroneous trigger (incoherent messages)]

INTERACTIVE FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Trigger\Target-like

Definition: The utterance that creates non-understanding is target-like.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

Bot: Please could you give me your name?

User: My name is Apichaya Lamsam [target-like trigger]

Bot: So sorry, I could not understand your last message. Could you please say it again?

User: is this the One King Hotel? [target-like trigger]

Bot: You can easily reach us by subway from the None.

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator	<p>Definition: The utterance that signals that something in a previous utterance was not understood, either explicitly (e.g., through a clarification request) or implicitly (e.g., through an in. response).</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: Which of the above rooms have got a projector? <u>Bot: All of the three rooms are equipped for presentations.</u> <u>Bot: Please could you give me the name of the room?</u></p> <p>User: I need a projector in the room. <u>Bot: For what date would you like to make the reservation?</u> User: The 12th October 2019 <u>Bot: I will reserve room None for the 12th October 2019. Could you please confirm if this is correct?</u> User: Is this room comfortable? <u>Bot: Beta is CHF 900 including the terrace.</u> User: Is this room comfortable? <u>Bot: Room Alpha is an auditorium where the quests sit in rows facing the stage. It has no tables.</u></p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator\Initiator	<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator\Initiator\Learner</p> <p>Definition: The learner initiates the negotiation sequence, i.e., indicates non-understanding.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Bot: Unfortunately, we do not offer any catering services. [trigger] <u>User: Than its just the room</u> [indicator part 1] <u>User: and the bar</u> [indicator part 2]</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator\Initiator\Interlocutor	<p>Definition: The interlocutor initiates the negotiation sequence, i.e., indicates non-understanding.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples:</p>

User: Hello, is this the One King Hotel in Toronto? [trigger]
 Bot: Excuse me, could you rephrase this please? [indicator]

Bot: Thank you for your reservation and have a nice day.
 User: you too [trigger]
 Bot: Please could you give me your name? [indicator]

Bot: For what date would you like to reserve room Alpha?
 User: we would like to come at the 12 june and then staying 5 days there [trigger]
 Bot: Could you please give me the date for the reservation? [indicator]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator\Type

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator\Type\Clarification request

Definition: A type of indicator that seeks to elicit clarification of the interlocutor's preceding utterance.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

User: How is the room looking? [trigger]
 Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase? [clarification request]

Bot: Room Gamma has room for 200 guests.
 User: Is Video and Audio player available? [trigger]
 Bot: Could you tell me which room you are interested in? [clarification request]

Bot: So, I will book room Gamma on the 13 of july 2020 for you. Could you please confirm if you would like me to proceed? [trigger]
 User: per mail or like what [clarification request]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Indicator\Type\Confirmation check

Definition: A type of indicator that serves to establish that the previous utterance was understood correctly.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

User: Yes, are drinks and food included in the price too?

Bot: Unfortunately, we do not offer any catering services. [trigger]

User: Than its just the room [confirmation check - part 1]

User: and the bar [confirmation check - part 2]

User: Okey the room Alpha would fit our expectations, is the room free on 12th October 2019?
[trigger]

Bot: So, I will book room Alpha on the 12th October 2019 for you. Could you please confirm if you would like me to proceed? [confirmation check]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation
of meaning\Indicator\Type\Inappropriate
response

Definition: The indicator utterance signals indirectly and implicitly that something was not understood by giving an inappropriate response to the previous utterance.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Example:

Bot: Thank you for your reservation and have a nice day.

User: you too [trigger]

Bot: Please could you give me your name? [inappropriate response]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation
of meaning\Indicator\Type\Overlap

Definition: The user overlooks the interlocutor's utterance due to message overlap and gives an inappropriate response that is a continuation of the user's own previous utterance.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Example:

Interlocutor: He is at the first level of the building. The interior is from the 1920es

Interlocutor: At the 12th of octobre 2k19 is he free

Learner: is the atmosphere good in this room?

Interlocutor: At the tables can sit 6 to 8 persones. [inappropriate response due to overlap]

Learner: that's very good can i book this room now?

Interlocutor: Yes the atmosphere ist very beautiful it is from 1920

Interlocutor: Yeah the room is booked for you.

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Meta-comment

Definition: The respondent responds to the indicator on a metalinguistic level on the indicator or overall non-understanding.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including time stamp.

Examples:

User: thank you very much, have a nice day [trigger]

Bot: I am sorry, I did not understand that. Could you please try one more time? [indicator]

User: Nevermind [meta-comment]

User: ohh thats nice [trigger]

Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message? [indicator]

User: sorry [meta-comment]

User: Has the Beta room also got monitors and speakers? [trigger]

Bot: The Beta room has space for a total of 190 people, indoor and outdoor. [indicator]

User: Hä [meta-comment]

User: and what about having apero? [trigger]

Bot: Room Gamma still has the original decoration from the 1920s. It is located on the first floor of the hotel and offers plenty of space. [indicator]

User: thats not what i asked [meta-comment]

User: The reservation is for 12 october 2019 [trigger]

Bot: Please could you confirm if you would like to book room Alpha for the 12 october 2019?

Bot: Room Alpha has a big screen and a state-of-the-art projector and audio system.

Bot: It is possible to add a portable screen as well as projector and loudspeakers to Beta. [indicator]

User: Do you need more informations? [meta-comment]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic abandonment

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation
of meaning\Response\Topic
abandonment\Change topic

Definition: The respondent abandons the topic of the message that created non-understanding and continues with a new topic.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

User: How many People can stay here? [trigger]

Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase? [indicator]

User: is this the One King Hotel? [change topic]

User: I asked, if this is the "One King Hotel" in Toronto. [trigger]

Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase? [indicator]

User: Our company would like to reserve one of your rooms for an event of ourcompany [change topic]

Bot: So, I will book room Gamma on the 13 of july 2020 for you. Could you please confirm if you would like me to proceed? [trigger]

User: per mail or like what [indicator]

Bot: Thank you, we have made the reservation.

Bot: Is there anything else I can do for you? [change topic]

Bot: Please could you confirm if you would like to book room Alpha for the 12 october 2019?

Bot: Room Alpha has a big screen and a state-of-the-art projector and audio system.

Bot: It is possible to add a portable screen as well as projector and loudspeakers to Beta. [trigger]

User: Do you need more informations? [indicator]

Bot: We have multiple rooms available for you.

Bot: Please could you give me the number of guests? [change topic]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation
of meaning\Response\Topic
abandonment\Accept topic

Definition: The respondent abandons the topic of the message that created non-understanding and continues with the topic that the interlocutor introduced during the indicator move.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

User: First name? [trigger]

Bot: How many guests are you expecting? [indicator]

User: About 150 or more [accept topic]

User: no, thats all thank you and goodbye! [trigger]

Bot: Please could you give me the name of the room? [indicator]

User: Gamma [accept topic]

Bot: Room Gamma still has the original decoration from the 1920s. It is located on the first floor of the hotel and offers plenty of space.

User: ok [trigger]

Bot: Yes, certainly.

Bot: For what date would you like me to reserve room Gamma for you? [indicator]

User: i take the room gamma [accept topic]

Bot: Room Alpha provides space for up to 270 people.

User: And the other rooms? [trigger]

Bot: Room Alpha has no natural light as it is located on the basement floor. There is however a fully equipped lighting system.

Bot: Room Beta has a lot of natural light from its glass ceiling. [indicator]

User: And room Gamma? [accept topic]

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic continuation

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic continuation\Reformulation

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic continuation\Reformulation\Type

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of

Definition: The response provides more specific information than the utterance that created non-understanding by means of elaboration.

meaning\Response\Topic
continuation\Reformulation\Type\EI
aboration

Coding guideline:

- Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.
- Included are responses where the respondent specifies which room he/she was referring to in the utterance that caused non-understanding, e.g., "Which room are you referring to?" - "Alpha"

Examples:

User: Hello, is this the One King Hotel in Toronto?

Bot: Excuse me, could you rephrase this please?

User: I asked, if this is the "One King Hotel" in Toronto. [elaboration]

User: Yes i already looked up what rooms you've got.

Bot: Excuse me, could you rephrase this please?

User: I have visited your web page and saw the rooms. [elaboration]

Bot: The Beta room has space for a total of 190 people, indoor and outdoor.

User: Hä

Bot: There are two rooms available for 150 people.

Bot: Room Alpha provides space for up to 270 people.

Bot: There is space for 200 people in room Gamma. [elaboration]

User: I confirm

Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message?

User: Yes i confirm it i would like you to proceed [elaboration]

User: Okay and how much does it costs?

Bot: So sorry, I could not understand your last message. Could you please say it again?

User: How much does the Alpha room costs? [elaboration]

User: What are the qualities of the Alpha room?

Bot: Room Alpha would be CHF 1400.

User: Have you got a chance to do an presentation in the Alpha room? [elaboration]

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Negotiation of
meaning\Response\Topic

Definition: The response reduces the information content of the utterance that caused non-understanding.

continuation\Reformulation\Type\Reduction

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

User: That sounds great. Is the room gamma fancy or like a normal room [trigger]

Bot: Very well. Would you like to book room Gamma? [indicator]

User: Is room gamma too fancy ? [reduction]

User: yes, i will book the alpha on the 12 October 2019 [trigger]

Bot: Would you like me to book room Alpha for the 12 October 2019? [indicator]

User: yes [reduction]

User: we would like to come at the 12 june and then staying 5 days there [trigger]

Bot: Could you please give me the date for the reservation? [indicator]

User: the date for the reservation is the 12 june [reduction]

User: I would like to book the room Alpha for 12 october 2019 and the number of guests is minimum 150 persons [trigger]

Bot: I am sorry, I did not understand that. Could you please try one more time? [indicator]

User: minimum 150 people [reduction]

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Negotiation of
meaning\Response\Topic
continuation\Reformulation\Type\Modification

Definition: The response involves formal modification (e.g., error correction, rephrasal by use of synonyms) of the utterance that caused non-understanding without expanding or reducing its information content.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Examples:

User: No, this is it. Thank you. We'll be there at 8 am and the event will start at 9 am. [trigger]

Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message? [indicator]

User: I don't need anything else. [modification]

User: Than its just the room [trigger part 1]

User: and the bar [trigger part 2]

Bot: The cost for Beta would be CHF 900. The terrace is included in the price. [indicator]

User: Yes, but are drinks and food included to the price too? [modification]

User: which room has the most place to have conversations [trigger]
 Bot: Would you like me to book room None for the None? [indicator]
 User: no, which room is the best for have also place for tidy conversation [modification]

User: I confirm the booking of room Alpha, thanks [trigger]
 Bot: Room Alpha is equipped with a big screen, a sound and lighting system as well as a stage. [indicator]
 User: We would like to book the room Alpha [modification]

User: and does gamma have a beamer? [trigger]
 Bot: The price for Gamma is 1100 CHF. [indicator]
 User: does the room have a projector? [modification]

User: How about presentations [trigger]
 Bot: The outdoor section in room Beta offers a great view over the whole city. The indoor area has modern furnishing and a lot of natural light from the glass roof. [indicator]
 User: are there monitors and speakers [modification]

User: yesss! [trigger]
 Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message? [indicator]
 User: yes [modification]

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Negotiation of
 meaning\Response\Topic
 continuation\Reformulation\Accuracy

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Negotiation of
 meaning\Response\Topic
 continuation\Reformulation\Accura
 cy\Improved

Definition: The response contains fewer (grammar, spelling, lexis, discourse) errors than the trigger utterance.

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.

Example:

User: In which room can i make also private speaks [trigger]
 Bot: I am sorry, I did not understand that. Could you please try one more time? [indicator]
 User: which room has the most place to have conversations [improved accuracy]

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic continuation\Reformulation\Accuracy\Reduced</p>	<p>Definition: The response contains more errors (i.e., grammatical, spelling, vocabulary, discourse errors) than the trigger utterance.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: which room has the most place to have conversations [trigger] Bot: Would you like me to book room None for the None? [indicator] <u>User: no, which room is the best for have also place for tidy conversation</u> [reduced accuracy]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic continuation\Reformulation\Accuracy\Equivalent</p>	<p>Definition: The response contains the same number of errors (i.e., grammatical, spelling, vocabulary, discourse errors) as the trigger utterance.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: like the mood or feeling [trigger] Bot: Yes, absolutely. Bot: Could you please tell me which room you are referring to? [indicator] <u>User: alpha</u> [equivalent accuracy]</p> <p>User: And the other rooms? [trigger] Bot: Room Alpha has no natural light as it is located on the basement floor. There is however a fully equipped lighting system. Bot: Room Beta has a lot of natural light from its glass ceiling. [indicator] <u>User: And room Gamma?</u> [equivalent accuracy]</p> <p>User: I confirm [trigger] Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message? [indicator] <u>User: Yes i confirm it i would like you to proceed</u> [equivalent accuracy]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\Topic continuation\Repetition</p>	<p>Definition: The response involves exact repetition of the utterance or parts of the utterance that caused non-understanding.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p>

	<p>Examples:</p> <p>User: Lamsam [trigger] Bot: Excuse me, could you rephrase this please? [indicator] <u>User: Lamsam</u> [repetition]</p> <p>User: and the others? [trigger] Bot: Room Gamma has two moveable monitors and speakers. [indicator] <u>User: and the others?</u> [repetition]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Response\No response</p>	<p>Definition: There is no response given at the end of an interaction or due to message overlap.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the indicator move instead including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples: User: you too [trigger] <u>Bot: Please could you give me your name?</u> [end of interaction – no response]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response\Resolution</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response\Resolution\Implicit resolution</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor implicitly indicates that the non-understanding has been resolved by providing an appropriate reaction to the preceding response move.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: can you tell me about the Alpha, Beta, Gamma rooms? [trigger] Bot: For what date would you like me to reserve room Gamma for you? [indicator] User: i need a room for 150 people [response - change topic] <u>Bot: There are three rooms available for 150 people.</u> [implicit resolution]</p> <p>User: Yes, I would like to have the Gamma room [trigger]</p>

	<p>Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message? [indicator] User: Can we show videos or something like that in this room? [response - change topic] <u>Bot: Room Beta has a bar and tables for up to four people each. On the terrace there are bar tables and lounge seats.</u> [implicit resolution]</p> <p>User: we would like to come at the 12 june and then staying 5 days there [trigger] Bot: Could you please give me the date for the reservation? [indicator] User: the date for the reservation is the 12 june [response - accept topic topic] <u>Bot: Very well. Would you like to book room Alpha?</u> [implicit resolution]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response\No resolution</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response\No resolution\Implicit no resolution</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor indicates implicitly that the non-understanding has not been resolved by giving an inappropriate reaction to the preceding response.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: Yes, I would like to have the Gamma room [trigger] Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message? [indicator] User: Can we show videos or something like that in this room? [response] <u>Bot: Room Beta has a bar and tables for up to four people each. On the terrace there are bar tables and lounge seats.</u> [implicit no resolution]</p> <p>User: In which room can i make also private speaks [trigger] Bot: I am sorry, I did not understand that. Could you please try one more time? [indicator] User: which room has the most place to have conversations [response] <u>Bot: Would you like me to book room None for the None?</u> [implicit no resolution]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response\No resolution\Explicit no resolution</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor states explicitly that the non-understanding has not been resolved.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire turn including timestamp.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: thank you very much, have a nice day [trigger]</p>

	<p>Bot: I am sorry, I did not understand that. Could you please try one more time? [indicator] User: Nevermind [response] <u>Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message?</u> [explicit no resolution]</p> <p>User: yes [trigger] Bot: I am pleased to hear that you like it. Bot: Is there anything else I can help you with? [indicator] User: WAIT [response] <u>Bot: Excuse me, can you please rephrase your last message?</u> [explicit no resolution]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Reaction to response\No reaction to response</p>	<p>Definition: There is no reaction to response because the negotiation takes place at the end of the interaction or there is a message overlap.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final move of the negotiation (i.e., indicator or response move) instead including timestamp.</p> <p>Example: User: you too [trigger] Bot: Please could you give me your name? [end of the interaction – indicator / no response / no reaction to response]</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Complexity</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Complexity\Single-layered</p>	<p>Definition: The negotiation sequence consists of a single trigger-indicator-response-reaction sequence.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire sequence including timestamps.</p> <p>Example: User: Alright. It is possible to remove the decorations and put something new of the year 2000? [trigger] Bot: Could you please give me the date for the reservation? [indicator] User: Our event will be on the 12th of October 2019. [response] Bot: Thank you. So, I will book Gamma for the 12th of October 2019. Could you please confirm if this is correct? [reaction to response]</p>

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Negotiation of meaning\Complexity\Multi-layered	<p>Definition: The negotiation sequence consists of more than one embedded single trigger-indicator-response-reaction sequences.</p>
	<p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the entire sequence including timestamps beginning at the initial trigger and ending at the final reaction move.</p>
	<p>Example:</p>
	<p>User: How many People can stay here? [trigger 1] Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase? [indicator 1] User: is this the One King Hotel? [response 1 / trigger 2] Bot: You can easily reach us by subway from the None. [reaction to response 1 / indicator 2] User: can you tell me about the Alpha, Beta, Gamma rooms? [response 2 / trigger 3] Bot: For what date would you like me to reserve room Gamma for you? [reaction to response 2 / indicator 3] User: i need a room for 150 people [response 3] Bot: There are three rooms available for 150 people. [reaction to response 3]</p> <p>User: Okey the room Alpha would fit our expectations, is the room free on 12th October 2019? [trigger 1] Bot: So, I will book room Alpha on the 12th October 2019 for you. Could you please confirm if you would like me to proceed? [indicator 1] User: I confirm the booking of room Alpha, thanks [response 1 / trigger 2] Bot: Room Alpha is equipped with a big screen, a sound and lighting system as well as a stage. [reaction to response 1 / indicator 2] User: We would like to book the room Alpha [response 2] Bot: Room Alpha has just been reserved for you. [reaction to response 2]</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment	<p>Definition: The reuse of a syntactical structure that occurred previously in the interaction either in the learner's or the interlocutor's production.</p>
	<p>Coding guideline: Considered are syntactical structures that occur at least five times within a given interaction in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production.</p>

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Copula "be"

Definition: The use of copula *be*.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to all inflectional forms of the copula verb *be*.
- Both the learner's and interlocutor's production are considered for coding.
- When the verb is used in a contracted form (e.g., 's', 'm'), the code is assigned to the contracted form excluding the apostrophe.
- When the verb is negated, the code is assigned to the verb *be* only, and the negator is not included in the code (e.g., *isn't*).
- The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error.

Examples:

Bot: Room Alpha has just been reserved for you.

User: Hello, i am searching for a room suitable for our company event that costs 1'500 Francs maximum. It will take place on 12th October 2019. The room should be big enough to fit a minimum of 150 people. We also need to be able to play video and audio in the room.

User: Hello my name is Jessica and i'm working for the company Coop

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Copula "be"\Used by learner

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Copula "be"\Used by
learner\Learner > interlocutor

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages the code "Learner > both" is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by learner\Learner > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by learner\Learner > both</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner</p>	<p>Coding guidelines:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor's reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned. When the interlocutor's reuse is incorrect, the category "repetition of error" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Copula "be"\Used by interlocutor\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\ "Have" + noun phrase</p>	<p>Definition: An occurrence of the verb <i>have</i> with a noun phrase as a complement.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the verb <i>have</i>, excluding the noun phrase. • Nouns include pronouns and nominalizations (e.g., for <i>contacting</i>). • When the verb <i>have</i> is used in a contracted form (e.g., '<i>ve</i>), the code is assigned to the contracted form excluding the apostrophe. • The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error.

Examples:

Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase?

Bot: Room Alpha has no natural light as it is located on the basement floor. There is however a fully equipped lighting system.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used by
learner

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used
by learner\Learner > interlocutor

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the learner’s message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner’s as well as interlocutor’s production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code “Learner > both” is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used
by learner\Learner > learner

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the structure in the learner’s message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner’s as well as interlocutor’s production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code “Learner > both” is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used by learner\Learner > both</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner’s as well as the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner’s message. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner’s nor in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner’s message. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used by interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor’s production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner’s as well as the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor’s reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner’s erroneous use of the structure, the category “recast” is assigned. When the interlocutor’s reuse is incorrect, the category “repetition of error” is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“Have” + noun phrase\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p>

- The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Have" + noun phrase\Used
by interlocutor\Unprimed

Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production.
- The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction.
- If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\For"
+ noun phrase

Definition: The use of the preposition *for* with a noun phrase as a complement.

Coding guideline:

- The code is assigned to the preposition *for* only, excluding the noun phrase.
- Nouns include pronouns and nominalizations (e.g., *for contacting*).
- The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error.

Examples:

User: can you tell me, which room is the best for my options?

Bot: For what date would you like me to reserve room Beta for you?

User: no problem, thank you for book the room for me

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\For" + noun phrase\Used by
learner

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
 alignment\“For” + noun phrase\Used by
 learner\Learner > interlocutor

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the learner’s message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner’s as well as interlocutor’s production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code “Learner > both” is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
 alignment\“For” + noun phrase\Used by
 learner\Learner > learner

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the structure in the learner’s message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner’s as well as interlocutor’s production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code “Learner > both” is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
 FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
 alignment\“For” + noun phrase\Used by
 learner\Learner > both

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner’s as well as the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the learner’s message.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“For” + noun phrase\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner’s nor in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“For” + noun phrase\Used by interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor’s production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner’s as well as the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor’s reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner’s erroneous use of the structure, the category “recast” is assigned. When the interlocutor’s reuse is incorrect, the category “repetition of error” is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\“For” + noun phrase\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor’s message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner’s as well as interlocutor’s production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code “Interlocutor > learner” is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\For" + noun phrase\Used by
interlocutor\Unprimed

Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production.
- The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction.
- If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Modal + infinitive

Definition: A verb phrase with a modal verb (i.e., an auxiliary verb that expresses modality such as

can / could
shall / should
may / might
will / would
must

as its head followed by an infinitive.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the modal verb.
- When the verb is used in a contracted form (e.g., 'll, 'd), the code is assigned to the contracted form excluding the apostrophe.
When the modal verb is negated, the code is assigned to the verb only, excluding the negator (e.g., *shouldn't*).
- The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error.

Examples:

User: The should have space for at least 150 peoples, have a projector for a presentation, allow conversations in small groups, have a good atmosphere, should look quite noble but not over the top and shouldn't cost more than 1500 Francs.

User: Ok, we'll go with room beta. Thanks for your advise.

Bot: What would be the date for the booking?

User: That would be the 12 of October 2019.

Bot: Sure. Would you like to book it?

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by learner</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by learner\Learner > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by learner\Learner > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the code to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by learner\Learner > both</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor's reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned. When the interlocutor's reuse is incorrect, the category "repetition of error" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Modal + infinitive\Used by interlocutor\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned. 	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive</p>	<p>Definition: Use of the <i>to</i>-infinitive, i.e., an infinitive verb preceded by the infinitival particle <i>to</i>.</p>
	<p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the marker <i>to</i> excluding any dependents. • The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error.
	<p>Example:</p> <p>Bot: Thank you for contacting One King Hotel. I am happy <u>to</u> help you find a room for your event. Bot: I will be happy <u>to</u> assist you. How can I help? User: I'd like <u>to</u> reservate a room in your hotel.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by learner</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by learner\Learner > interlocutor</p>	<p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by learner\Learner > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by learner\Learner > both</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by interlocutor</p>	<p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p>
	<p>Coding guidelines:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor's reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned. When the interlocutor's reuse is incorrect, the category "repetition of error" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\To"-infinitive\Used by interlocutor\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"</p>	<p>Definition: Use of the dummy pronoun <i>there</i> as subject.</p> <p>Coding guideline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to there. • The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error. <p>Examples:</p>

	<p>User: Is <u>there</u> a good atmosphere?</p> <p>Bot: <u>There</u> are three rooms available for 150 people.</p>
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by learner</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by learner\Learner > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by learner\Learner > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the code to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by learner\Learner > both</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by interlocutor</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor's reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned. When the interlocutor's reuse is incorrect, the category "repetition of error" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Existential "there"\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in

the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned.

- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Existential "there"\Used by
interlocutor\Unprimed

Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production.
- The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction.
- If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Question with subject-auxiliary
inversion

Definition: An interrogative clause that is marked by subject-auxiliary inversion.

Coding guideline:

- The code is assigned to the part of the clause containing the subject or dummy *there* and auxiliary verb (includes copula *be*) and any elements that stand between them.
- The category excludes subordinate interrogative clauses.
- The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error.

Examples:

User: I have questions about your hotel. Did you have a room for 150 persons?

Bot: Is there anything else I can do for you?

User: Will we be able to play video and audio in room alpha?

User: Okey the room Alpha would fit our expectations, is the room free on 12th October 2019?

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Question with subject-auxiliary
inversion\Used by learner

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Question with subject- auxiliary inversion\Used by learner\Learner > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Question with subject- auxiliary inversion\Used by learner\Learner > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the code to the structure in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Question with subject- auxiliary inversion\Used by learner\Learner > both</p>	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\Question with subject- auxiliary inversion\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure.

- The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction.
- If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Question with subject-auxiliary
inversion\Used by interlocutor

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Question with subject-
auxiliary inversion\Used by
interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner

Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor’s production.
- The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner’s as well as the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.
- When the interlocutor’s reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner’s erroneous use of the structure, the category “recast” is assigned. When the interlocutor’s reuse is incorrect, the category “repetition of error” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Question with subject-
auxiliary inversion\Used by
interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor

Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor’s message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner’s as well as interlocutor’s production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code “Interlocutor > learner” is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an N-gram of three or more words), the category “lexical alignment” is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Question with subject-

Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner’s nor the interlocutor’s production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

auxiliary inversion\Used by interlocutor\Unprimed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\"Wh"-interrogative	<p>Definition: An interrogative clause that is marked by the presence of an interrogative word, i.e.,</p> <p><i>who</i> <i>what</i> <i>when</i> <i>where</i> <i>why</i> <i>how</i> <i>which</i></p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the interrogative word. • The category excludes subordinate interrogative clauses. • The code is also assigned if the structure contains an error. <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: okey <u>which</u> room is the best for a good atmosphere</p> <p>Bot: For <u>what</u> date would you like to reserve room Gamma?</p> <p>User: the room Gamma, <u>how</u> much costs it?</p> <p>User: <u>What</u>'s the atmpshere like in Room Alpha?</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\"Wh"-interrogative\Used by learner	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\"Wh"-interrogative\Used by learner\Learner > interlocutor	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p>

- The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Wh"-interrogative\Used by
learner\Learner > both

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure in the learner's message.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Wh"-interrogative\Used by
learner\Learner > learner

Definition: The learner reuses the structure after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the structure in the learner's message.
- The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned.
- If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic
alignment\Wh"-interrogative\Used by
learner\Unprimed

Definition: The learner uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the structure.
- The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction.
- If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\ "Wh"-interrogative\Used by interlocutor</p>	
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\ "Wh"-interrogative\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned when the structure occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor's reuse of the structure involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned. When the interlocutor's reuse is incorrect, the category "repetition of error" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\ "Wh"-interrogative\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the structure after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's message. • The code is only assigned if the structure was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the structure occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned. • If the reuse involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Syntactic alignment\ "Wh"-interrogative\Used by interlocutor\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor uses the structure, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the structure in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned to structures that appear for the first time in an interaction. • If the use involves the exact repetition of a lexical unit (defined here as an n-gram of three or more words), the category "lexical alignment" is assigned.

INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment	<p>Definition: The reuse of lexical material that occurred previously in the interaction either in the learner's or the interlocutor's production.</p> <p>Coding guideline: Considered are n-grams of three to five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) words that occur at least twice within a given interaction, excluding n-grams that occur exclusively in the interlocutor's production.</p>
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by learner	
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by learner\Learner > learner	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the n-gram after it occurred in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the code to the n-gram in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the n-gram was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the n-gram occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned.
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by learner\Learner > interlocutor	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the n-gram after it occurs in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the n-gram in the learner's message. • The code is only assigned if the n-gram was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the n-gram occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Learner > both" is assigned.
INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by learner\Learner > both	<p>Definition: The learner reuses the n-gram after it occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines: The code is assigned to the n-gram in the learner's message.</p>

<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by learner\Unprimed</p>	<p>Definition: The learner uses the n-gram, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the n-gram. • The code is also assigned to the n-grams that appear for the first time in an interaction.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by interlocutor</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reuses the n-gram after it occurs exclusively in the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the n-gram in the interlocutor's message. • The code is only assigned if the n-gram was used exclusively by the interlocutor within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. When the n-gram occurs in the learner's as well as interlocutor's production within the last five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages, the code "Interlocutor > learner" is assigned.
<p>INTERACTIONAL FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical alignment\Used by interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner</p>	<p>Definition: The interlocutor reproduces an erroneous n-gram with the same or a new error after it occurs in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The code is assigned to the n-gram in the interlocutor's production. • The code is also assigned when the n-gram occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages. • When the interlocutor's reuse of the n-gram involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned.

Example:

User: for the 12 octobre 2019

Bot: I will reserve room Gamma for the 12 octobre 2019. Could you please confirm if this is correct?

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical
alignment\Used by
interlocutor\Interlocutor > learner\Error-
free

Definition: The interlocutor reproduces an n-gram error-free after it occurs error-free in the learner's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the n-gram in the interlocutor's production.
- The code is also assigned when the n-gram occurred in the learner's as well as the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.
- When the interlocutor's reuse of the n-gram involves the target-like reformulation of the learner's erroneous use of the structure, the category "recast" is assigned. When the interlocutor's reuse is incorrect, the category "repetition of error" is assigned.

Example:

User: i need a room for 150 people

Bot: We have three event rooms on offer for 150 people.

INTERACTIONAL
FEATURES\Alignment\Lexical
alignment\Used by interlocutor\Unprimed

Definition: The interlocutor uses the n-gram, but it occurs neither in the learner's nor the interlocutor's production within the preceding five (system interaction) / ten (SCMC) messages.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the n-gram in the interlocutor's production.
- The code is also assigned to n-gram that appear for the first time in an interaction.